

Towards a Sustainable Sierra Leone National Soil Information System (NaSIS)

The Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel

13th – 14th October 2025, Freetown, Sierra Leone

Workshop report

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Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel

Hub Régional pour les Engrais et la Santé des Sols pour l'Afrique de l'Ouest et le Sahel

List of Abbreviation

CABI	Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International
CEDAS	Centre for Environmental Data and Statistics
DST	Decision Support Tool
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
EU	European Union
FSRP	Food System Resilience Program
GIS	Geographic Information System
IITA	International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
ISRIC	International Soil Reference and Information Centre
MAFS	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NaSIS	Sierra Leone National Soil Information System
NaFFL	National Federation of Farmers of Sierra Leone
NaFRA	National Fertilizer and Regulatory Agency
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
SLARI	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute
SLEITI	Sierra Leone's Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative
SIS	Soil Information System
WA hub	West Africa Hub

Executive Summary

This SIS development report outlines the strategic steps for building and strengthening Sierra Leone's Soil Information System (NaSIS) to enhance agricultural productivity, soil health, and informed decision-making for sustainable soil management. It builds on insights from the "Sierra Leone Soil Information System Development Workshop" held in October 2025 in Freetown, Sierra Leone, hosted by the Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, IITA Sierra Leone, Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS), Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI), and ISRIC-World Soil Information. Participants from various sectors addressed common data and capacity challenges and discussed long-term financial sustainability options for NaSIS.

The workshop reviewed seven components of the [SIS framework](#), crucial for NaSIS's success: 1) envisioning the SIS, 2) enabling environment, 3) needs assessment, 4) SIS ideal system design, 5) partnership development and sustainability plan, 6) data strategy, and 7) organizational and financial sustainability plan. The roadmap includes an overview of each component, addressing available information, gaps, and recommendations, which are optional considerations for the NaSIS project team.

The key potential next steps for MAFS, SLARI and Njala University to consider include:

- Set up data sharing agreement between SLARI, Njala University and the WA hub (ISRIC and IITA) by end of October 2025.
- Share data of the national soil survey, including coordinates and metadata, by 1 November 2025 to generate soil maps under WA HUB by end of December 2025.
- Add 1-2 page (amendment) on existing MoU between SLARI and Njala University on data sharing including that all new soil data should be added to SIS by December 2025.
- Set up ToR for steering and technical committee by end of November 2025.
- Review Africa SIS and its field campaign standards to select the standard SLARI/Njala university want to use for all future soil data collection in Sierra Leone by December 2025.
- Write up standard in Soil Data Collection Policy for future soil campaigns by December 2025.
- Set up steering and technical committee for NaSIS by January 2026.
- Set up soil database within Njala university in 2026.
- Create template data sharing MoU for other stakeholders to add data/info into the SIS in 2026.
- Identify data gaps and set up sampling design for WA hub in 2026.
- Conduct field campaign under WA Hub including capacity building in 2026-2027.

The SIS owner (MAFS) and SIS operator (SLARI/Njala University) intend to establish a steering committee and a technical committee for the NaSIS strengthening process. The steering committee will be responsible for setting the strategic direction, overseeing system integrity and alignment between the organisations while the technical committee ensures stakeholder coordination, provides technical upgrades, and monitors compliance with data governance and quality standards.

Acknowledgments

MAFS, SLARI, ISRIC-World Soil Information, Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IITA would like to thank workshop participants for their contributions that have led to the development of this roadmap. With special thanks to Regional Hub for Fertilizer and Soil Health for West Africa and the Sahel, and IITA for their support in organizing the workshop, and to CABI for their input and review.

More information, supporting resources and useful tools for each of the components are available in the online SIS framework, hosted on ISRIC's Resource Library and created by CABI and ISRIC – World Soil Information (<https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/>).

If there are any questions or aspects of the roadmap that require further support or input from ISRIC, kindly contact chrow.khurshid@isric.org or thaisa.vanderwoude@isric.org

Introduction

A Soil Information System (SIS) is not just a digital platform but a collaborative tool that engages stakeholders, from government agencies to farmers to improve data access, soil health management, and informed decision-making in Sierra Leone's agriculture sector. Understanding how people and institutions should work together, and aligning on who is responsible for what, is a critical step to ensuring the progress of the SIS. There are three levels of the enabling environment of the system to consider: the individual (suitable skills, knowledge, competencies, and attitudes), the organizational (efficient structures, processes, and procedures), and the governmental level (establishment of adequate institutions, laws, and regulations).

[CAB-International](#) and [ISRIC – World Soil Information](#), supported by the Gates Foundation, has created a framework for SIS development, assessing these levels at the start of a SIS intervention. The ["https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/"](https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/) [SIS Framework](#) helps to identify activities needed to fulfil the SIS objectives, deciding also on the sequence in which these activities are best performed, who is going to do them, and identifying potential risks, with each specifically tailored to the country context. The SIS framework was the base for the NaSIS development workshop which was held in October 2025 in Freetown, Sierra Leone.

The objectives of the NaSIS development workshop were:

- Understanding the current status of the SIS.
- Verifying SIS goals and needs.
- Verifying stakeholders' requirements.
- Identifying key partners that need to be involved in the development of a full-scale SIS.
- Exploring technical options for sustainable operation.
- Identifying ways for developing a financially sustainable SIS.
- Agreeing on next steps for the development of the SIS.

This document gathers the information collected and validated during the workshop that details the steps required to achieve a specific goal. In this instance, the goal is a sustainable national SIS in Sierra Leone that will last beyond the initial phases of project funding, be built on best practices, and continue to meet the needs of users.

Workshop Day 1:

The workshop commenced with welcome remarks from SLARI, Njala university, IITA, ISRIC and NaFFSL. This was followed by an introduction of participants and an overview of the program and its expected outputs by IITA.

Session 1 – Setting the Scene

Soil is the foundation of all life, everything begins with the soil and ultimately returns to it. Providing reliable soil data and information is essential for addressing key issues such as climate change, fertilizer recommendations, and environmental impacts. At present, the soil information in Sierra Leone is fragmented and not effectively shared among different stakeholders. Stronger collaboration and better data exchange are needed to ensure that farmers can easily access, find, and use reliable soil information. Accurate soil data is crucial for site-specific recommendations. When we truly understand what's in our soils, we can make informed decisions that drive sustainable agricultural progress. High-quality soil data is critical — poor data leads to poor decisions. Garbage in, garbage out. To ensure that the National Soil Information System (NaSIS) makes a real impact, it is vital to involve all relevant stakeholders, including farmers, in its development.

Session 2 – Benefits of using the SIS framework

Thaïsa van der Woude from ISRIC presented the SIS framework, a brief explanation on what FAIR data is, the [FAIR process framework](#), and why FAIR is good for soil data projects. This followed by a Q&A session with the participants.

Session 3 – Current state of NaSIS and Live demo

There are various sources of soil data and information in Sierra Leone; however, they are not yet integrated into or accessible via a centralized platform. Limited data sharing among stakeholders continues to hinder progress toward this goal.

Recently, a national soil survey was conducted by Njala University in collaboration with the Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI) and the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS) under the Boosting Agriculture and Food Security (BAFS) Project and the Food System Resilience Program (FSRP). The reports of this survey are currently being reviewed by Prof. Rhodes from Njala University and are expected to be finalized by December 2025. At present, the lab dataset lacks essential components such as geographic coordinates and metadata descriptions. These need to be completed, cleaned, and incorporated into the National Soil Information System (NaSIS) by December 2025 to support digital soil mapping. The Minister of Agriculture, Dr. Musa Kpaka, through Prof. Abdulai Jalloh (the Chief Agricultural Officer - MAFS), has approved sharing the data among relevant stakeholders to facilitate further work. As part of the same project, a web interface for NaSIS was developed (<https://nasis.mafs.gov.sl/>), featuring initial soil maps such as

land and crop suitability maps. However, the current NaSIS does not yet have a back-end soil database linking individual soil samples to the system. Once established, this database should be connected to both MAFS and SLARI. Additionally, significant legacy soil data exists across the country and should also be integrated into NaSIS to ensure completeness and continuity.

For soil sampling, the [FAO Global Soil Partnership \(GSP\) standards](#) were applied, and these should continue to guide all future sampling campaigns. NaSIS should build upon these past efforts, serving as a long-term, sustainable platform that ensures reliable access to high-quality soil data.

NaSIS can also be linked with the Centre for Environmental Data and Statistics (CEDAS) (<https://ceda-sl.org/>) under the Ministry of Environment and Climate Change. CEDAS aims to promote data-driven decision-making by compiling various types of environmental data for policymakers. Although soil forms the foundation of many environmental processes, it is currently underrepresented in CEDAS. Therefore, stronger collaboration and data sharing between NaSIS and CEDAS would be mutually beneficial.

Session 4 – SIS stakeholder map and requirements

The objective of this session was to verify the user requirements and use cases beyond fertility maps, and others. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- What are the essential use cases for the SIS?
- What is the desired outcome and long-term vision for the SIS?
- How can the SIS support Sierra Leone's agricultural policies?
- What other stakeholders exist? What can they contribute to the SIS? How would they use the SIS?

Three groups, each consisting of 7-9 participants, were formed to discuss the topic.

Key outcomes from group discussions:

- **What are the essential use cases for the SIS?**
 - Land and soil management (on farm level)
 - Land use planning
 - Specific crop recommendations
 - Crop suitability mapping
 - Fertilizer formulation and recommendation
 - Monitoring soil fertility
 - Crop water use efficiency
 - Assessment of soil health and soil degradation status
 - Environmental management – climate change adaptation
 - Identify areas prone to landslides and erosion, based on their soil structure and texture

- Understanding the soil predictability in the context of climate change.
 - Research purposes – enriching research in Sierra Leone
 - Effective research management
 - Buy-in from policy makers
 - Ecosystem stabilities
 - Advancing agriculture productivity
 - Economic value
 - Investment planning
 - Gap identification
- **What is the desired outcome and long-term vision for the SIS?**
 - Co-hosted by SLARI and Njala university
 - Evidence-based policy formulation
 - Efficient use of soil resources
 - Availability of soil data (real time data, soil resources)
 - Improve agronomic practices
 - Enhanced sustainable crop production
 - Increased accessibility to soil data
 - All future soil data and information should end in the SIS which can only be done if it is written into a law or policy
 - *An example can be found in the Dutch law for soil data;*
<https://basisregistratieondergrond.nl/english/legislation/>
 - MAFS works with universities, SLARI and research institutes under a commonly agreed data sharing MoUMoU
 - *Example of data sharing policy can be found here;*
<https://gatesopenresearch.org/documents/8-26>
 - Providing a central resource for in-country actors to better understand Sierra Leone's soils – like a one stop shop. A national platform for accessing data on soil.
 - The SIS should be self-sustainable: small fees could be asked for in-depth analysis and monitor the data of interest.
 - *An conducted research on it can be found here:*
<https://access.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.2136/vzj2012.0198>
 - Strong policies in place on soil such as a policy on data collection (which standards to be used) for soil surveys
 - Formulation of sound policies on soil management
 - Efficient use of farmer input and national resources
 - Identification and curation of existing data can help to identify soil data gaps and determine the likely time and effort required to fill in soil sample gaps (for example under the WA hub).
- **How can the SIS support Sierra Leone's agricultural policies?**
 - Fertilizer quality regulation
 - Land use planning
 - Agronomic data and understanding of soil variability all help in policies.

- Data in NaSIS can be analysed to inform decision making.
- Livelihoods of farmers are improved by improved yield.
- **What other stakeholders exist? What can they contribute to the SIS? How they use the SIS?**
 - Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS)
 - Farmers
 - NGO's – data producer and user
 - NaFRA
 - Bankers – soil info could support evaluation of loan applications by farmers – to show where lenders are not likely to represent a high risk
 - Agrodealers or input dealers – to have better info for fertilizer recommendations
 - Investors – to know the status of the soil
 - Funders such as FAO – UNDP – IITA – EU – IFAD
 - Small and medium scale enterprise (SME) – data producer and user.
 - Farmers – for site specific recommendations (user)
 - Construction companies for geotechnical advice
 - Research institutes / Universities / Academic institutions – data producers and users
 - Environmental scientists
 - Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and CEDAS.
 - Environmental consultants – soil data producer
 - Ministry of Environment and climate change
 - Sierra Leone Meteorological Agency (SLMeT)
 - Sierra Leone water company – they work under the National Water Agency
 - Irrigation planners can use and provide data
 - GIS specialist – data producer and user

Session 5 – Data requirements

The objective of this session was to identify the data challenges. Below questions were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- How should user permissions and data access be managed?
- What are the data challenges?
- What are the data requirements from user perspective?
- What data policies, strategies and mandates exist?
- How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts?
- How will trust be built and differences resolved between stakeholders to align approaches to FAIR data standards and policies?

Summary of group discussions:

Each of the three groups (7-9 participants per group) used guiding questions to explore the topic. Key advice from all group discussions is summarized below:

- **How should user permissions and data access be managed?**

- FAIR data principles – an creative commons licences
- Recommendations and permission needs to be obtained for every use case(s).
- Key stakeholder roles should be defined so that different level of permission can be added.
- Raw soil sampling data should be accessible to anyone, with acknowledgement given to the source.
- It should not be possible to directly upload your own data. All data uploads need a quality check have and gone through a defined quality check process. This should be done by MAFS/ SLARI/ Njala university.
- Access to data could be throttled. It may be desirable to limit how much you can access at one time – for example you can only download x amount per minute
- User accounts or logins should be in place so that users are tracked.
- Registered users are useful to understand your audience; this may be achieved without login for all.
 - *An example can be found in the Australian and New Zealand SIS with login:*
<https://ansis.net/data/>
<https://soils.landcareresearch.co.nz/>
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0016706111003302>
- Some data should be fully open in the system, but not all data so data can be restricted /limited to certain actors.
 - For example: in depth analysis can be obtain via direct contact with MAFS/SLARI. Some fees can be applied.
- Identifying a system coordinator for easy communication and request
- Cleaned and harmonized data should be in a centralized platform clearly stating data ownership and permission for the data, such that everyone can see what exists (metadata should be available, even where underlying data is restricted).
- Data sharing MoU's are needed for the SIS.
- Universities hold various soil data sets – these would be great a great asset to the SIS. A possibility is to offer them a free access to all other data and products if they share their data in the SIS.
- Sharing of the soil data is needed to provide reliable information to farmers.
- FAIR data does not always mean open data; some limitations may be put on use, but it is acknowledged that there will be value in some maximising of data access. Combining of various data points will improve the soil maps for the country.

- NaSIS and CEDAS would benefit from sharing data among themselves to ensure soil information is used for decision making in the country.

- **What are the data challenges?**
 - Data format varies
 - Temporal dynamics of soil data
 - Data sharing culture is poor – people not willing to share data
 - Inaccessibility to raw data
 - Limited data/ fragmented data
 - Data is stored locally on computers
 - Inefficient data (missing parameters)
 - Limited digital data collection capacity
 - Non digitized data (legacy data)
 - Poor collaboration
 - Data collection methods vary
 - Lack of skilled people to manage the data (no data stewards)
 - Costs of cloud system
 - Metadata is missing
 - Soil monitoring – updating of the data is lacking – there is no follow up
 - Limited digital infrastructure
 - Data storage system and accessibility to the data.
 - Lack of standardize soil data production and analysis.
 -

- **What are the data requirements from user perspective?**
 - Slope
 - Erosion risk
 - Soil water storage capacity
 - Soil texture
 - Heavy metal content
 - Soil fertility levels
 - Topsoil depth
 - Crop yield
 - We need to select one standard for soil data collection and for data uploading (the FAO standard that has been used in the previous survey)
 - Clean data and reliable data
 - Standardised data

- **What data policies, strategies and mandates exist?**
 - No high-level policy or specific policies on soil are in place

- At the moment, there is only MoU existing between an institution and their consultants, but not between institutions.
- The Ministry of Information and Civic Education have policies in place for data sharing – it would be good to reach out to them:
 - Right to access information Act from 2023.
 - National digital development policy from 2021
 - National digital development strategy from 2022
 - Geo-data management policy
 - Sierra Leone’s Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (SLEITI)
 - Open Data Policy from 2026
 - Cyber security and cyber-crimes act
 - Developing data protection policy (national consultations started September 2025).
- **How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts?**
 - High-level policy to mandate individuals
 - Data sharing agreements between national and international partners
 - Approval by the government
 - Sensitization on the need for data sharing and collaboration
 - *An example can be found in Ethiopia’s Coalition of the Willing:*
<https://ethioagridata.com/>
 - Ministry of Environment and climate change has already some structure in place for data sharing. They are building an infrastructure for data sharing and might have capacity. This can also then be linked to the SIS.
 - Development of and signing of MoU’s
- **How will trust be built and differences resolved between stakeholders to align approaches to FAIR data standards and policies?**
 - Cost sharing.
 - Recognition and proper attribution (referencing) of data sources.
 - Co-publication of data.
 - Clear data sharing agreement.
 - Update institute mandate and clarify: which data will be hosted in CEDAS and which data in NaSIS to avoid two sources for soil data? The other system can then link to the soil database using API’s.
 - Common standards and metadata are important for soil data.
 - Harmonization of data is important – also making sure to use the same name (standardised methodology).
 - A centralized platform for soil data in the SIS.
 - Include the Ministry of Communication, technology and innovation during planning for the SIS development – this can also help for awareness raising.
 - Transparency is important to build trust.

- Stakeholders should follow FAIR principles – making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- Involvement of key stakeholders from the start.

Session 6- Partnership model

The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- Who is the owner of the SIS?
- Who should be the long-term technical administrator of the SIS?
- What institutional arrangement or coordination mechanism is needed to govern the partnership?
- How can we ensure that the partnership is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to stakeholder needs over time?
- What agreements or commitments (e.g. MoUs, data-sharing protocols) are needed to formalize the collaboration?

In the plenary discussion, the participants outlined the partnership for NaSIS as below:

- **Who is the owner of the SIS? Who should be the long-term technical administrator of the SIS?**
 - MAFS is the institutional owner of the SIS, while Njala University and SLARI are the technical/maintainer owner of the SIS. Njala University will host the SIS.
- **What institutional arrangement or coordination mechanism is needed to govern the partnership?**
 - A steering committee and a technical committee should be formed to ensure long-term sustainability of the SIS.
 - The steering committee should meet 2x per year and consist of:
 - Minister of Agriculture (Chairman)
 - Chief Agriculture Officer.
 - DG of SLARI
 - Vice Chancellor & Principal of Njala University
 - Head of Soil Science Department of Njala University
 - Ministry of Environment and Climate Change
 - Representative of National Federation of Farmers of Sierra Leone- NaFFL
 - Chair technical committee
 - The technical committee meets 4x per year and the chair reports to the Steering committee. It consists of:
 - Technical leads from:
 - MAFS
 - SLARI

- Njala University
- CEDAS/EPA
- National Fertilizer and Regulatory Agency - NAFRA
- **How can we ensure that the partnership is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to stakeholder needs over time?**
 - Technical steering committee will be the one responsible for stakeholder engagement on the SIS, while the steering committee will raise awareness on a higher policy-maker level.
- **What agreements or commitments (e.g. MoUs, data-sharing protocols) are needed to formalize the collaboration?**
 - An MoU on ownership between MAFS, SLARI and Njala university.
 - A national soil data sharing policy
 - A national soil data collection policy
 - An MoU for stakeholders on data sharing if they want to share their data to the SIS

Workshop Day 2:

Welcome and reflections from day one was carried out by SLARI.

Session 7 – Ideal System Design

Chrow Khurshid from ISRIC-World Soil Information presented the Soil information Workflow (SIWF). The objectives of this session were to brainstorm the ideal system design-based pilot and determine its key functionalities. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) do you want to see in your SIS or what is missing from the current SIS?
- What are you expecting the SIS will serve you with?
- Where should the database and the SIS be hosted?
- Are there any technical capacity gaps?

Three groups, each consisting of 7-9 participants, were formed to discuss the topic using the questions provided. A summary of the group discussions is outlined below:

- **What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) are missing from the current SIS?**
 - No interactive map
 - No central database
 - Inefficient data (missing parameters)
 - No current established SIS
- **What are you expecting the SIS will serve you? What do you want to see in the SIS?**
 - An interactive map:
 - to click on your location and see, for example, your soil pH.
 - To show soil profiles and information
 - To show maps on soil health properties and general crop recommendations
 - Soil monitoring dashboard
 - Functionality for updating and uploading additional soil data by technical lead
 - Data security back-ups
 - Offline accessibility
 - Safe repository for the national soil data
 - Streamline for investment/target intervention
 - Guide for policy formulation
 - Access to:
 - soil data (raw data)
 - climate data
 - land use planning

- agronomic data (yield data)
- Climate and weather data
- Crop suitability analysis
- Soil nutrient maps
- Agro advisory services
- Fertilizer recommendations
- Fertilizer formulation policy – solution for soil fertilizer supply
- Crop recommendations, such as rice advice recommendations
- Access to decision support systems
- Login feature with different levels of accessibility.
- Soil health information
- Downloadable maps
- Policy briefs (data summary) or report
- Dashboard and graphic tables
- Offline accessibility
- Mobile accessibility
- Tools for reducing climate vulnerability
- **Where should the database and the SIS be hosted?**
 - Technically with Njala University – department of soil science, co-hosted by SLARI. This hosting option would keep the SIS close to the key experts.
 - The software should be cloud-based for ease of access and security.
 - Physical storage for soil samples.
 - CEDAS.EPA should be part of the steering committee.
- **Are there any technical capacity gaps?**
 - GIS specialist / geospatial analyst in digital soil mapping
 - Remote sensing expert
 - Data management expert / data curator
 - Administration staff
 - ICT personnel to maintain and operate the system
 - Software developer
 - Programmer
 - Soil Scientist
 - Data Scientist
 - Lab analyst

After the session on the idealised system, a request was made to demo how a Soil Information system could look like. A live demo was provided on the AfricaSIS: <https://africasis.isric.org/> . It might help to review the AfricaSIS and other SISs (see <https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/case-studies.html>) for inspiration for Sierra Leone's NaSIS.

Session 8- Long term sustainability

The objective of this session was to explore financial strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of NaSIS. The questions below were used to initiate the discussion with the stakeholders' groups:

- **Long term sustainability - Cost Structure – Understanding Financial Needs**
 - Which institution in Sierra Leone should be responsible for the long-term financial management of the SIS?
 - What are the key cost categories in the SIS lifecycle (e.g. personnel, tech infrastructure, data management, capacity building)?
 - Which costs are already covered (e.g. by the government, OCP Foundation) and which are still unfunded?
- **Long term sustainability - Blending Core and Value-Added Financing**
 - What government budget lines could potentially support the SIS (e.g. agriculture, digital infrastructure, environment)?
 - Could a dedicated SIS funding unit or fundraising mechanism (e.g. grant writing team) be established?
- **Long term sustainability - Revenue Streams and Public-Private Collaboration**
 - What services or information could the SIS tailor for private sector clients (e.g. fertilizer companies, agribusinesses)?
 - What types of users (e.g. extension agents, local governments, NGOs) would be willing to pay for enhanced, user-specific data?
 - Are there existing consulting, training, or soil analysis services that SIS could build upon to generate income?

Summary of group discussions:

Three groups (each with 7-9 participants) discussed the financial and funding aspects of NaSIS. The key findings are summarized below:

- **Which institution in Sierra Leone should be responsible for the long-term financial management of the SIS?**
 - MAFS
 - Provide national budget for the SIS
 - SLARI
 - Njala University
 - University employs SIS staff paid for by the government
 - All stakeholder institutions commit part of their budget to support the SIS
 - Monetize some of the services of the SIS, such as deep analyses, to create funds
 - To establish SIS as a National Agency

- **What are the key cost categories in the SIS lifecycle (e.g. personnel, tech infrastructure, data management, capacity building)?**
 - Personnel costs (salaries)
 - Technical infrastructure :
 - Cloud service
 - Electronics (computer, software, service)
 - Building to host staff for the SIS
 - Hardware - Data storage
 - Soil Lab
 - Training and capacity building (short and long term)
 - Operational costs like maintenance and update
 - Research and development

- **Which those costs categories are already covered (e.g. by the government, OCP Foundation)?**
 - Some technical personnel costs
 - Office space at Njala University (electricity and other utilities) for the National Soil Database and Information System (SDIS/NaSDIS) established by the National Comprehensive Soil Survey (NCSS) Project.
 - Raw data
 - Soil lab has equipment

- **What government budget lines could potentially support the SIS (e.g. agriculture, digital infrastructure, environment)?**
 - Potential institutional overhead (50,000 -70,000 USD)
 - Create a new budget line for the SIS within SLARI and Njala University
 - MAFS

- **Could a dedicated SIS funding unit or fundraising mechanism (e.g. grant writing team) be established?**
 - Yes, consisting of staff from SLARI and Njala University with a yearly subscription
 - Employ a project and grant officer
 - Soil analysis in the lab to factor a small fee on lab analysis to support the SIS
 - It was felt that at least in the short term government funding is not enough to sustain the SIS.

- **What services or information could the SIS tailor for private sector clients (e.g. fertilizer companies, agribusinesses)?**

- For Fertilizer companies:
 - Soil fertility mapping
 - Soil data for site specific and crop specific fertilizer formulation
 - For Agriculture companies:
 - Fertilizer recommendations
 - Soil/crop suitability maps
 - Soil data
 - Legacy data
 - For Agribusiness investors:
 - Crop site suitability
 - Land use planning and management
 - Input data for AI
 - Training workshops and consultancy
 - Soil and crop data statistic
 - Climate change information
 - Research and Development support
- **What types of users (e.g. extension agents, local governments, NGOs) would be willing to pay for enhanced, user-specific data?**
 - Fertilizer companies
 - Agri producers
 - Land managers
 - International agri-business
 - Investment consultancy
 - AI, eg. Google service
 - Limited adverts especially from private sector
 - Research scientists
 - Projects
 - NGO's
 - Agri input companies
 - Financial institutions (Non-Banking Financial Companies [NBFC's])
 - **Are there existing consulting, training, or soil analysis services that SIS could build upon to generate income?**
 - Yes, quality control lab for Njala University and SLARI.
 - Environmental Social Health Impact Assessments (ESHIA) consultants
 - Existing consultants
 - Lab services
 - Short term courses

- Data insights
- IP of software

Session 10 - Next steps

The questions below were used to identify the next steps for NaSIS with the stakeholders' groups:

- What are the immediate action items based on the discussions in the previous sessions?
- Which short-term priorities should be addressed first, and what is the timeline for each?
- Who will be responsible for each key action, and how can accountability be ensured?

The actions are provided in the table below.

Table 1 Action points

Action point	Accountable (the institution "responsible" reports to)	Responsible (assigned to carry out the task)	Support	Timeline	Priority level 1=high 2=medium 3=low
Review of the recently collected data – National Soil survey report (review process ongoing)	MAFS / FSRNP	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh	Prof. Edward Rhoades	End of December	1
Data sharing agreement between SLARI, NJALA University and ISRIC (Chrow will share format) / DONE	Dr. Chow Khurshid	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh Prof. Jallo		End of October	1
Data sharing agreement between SLARI, NJALA University and IITA (PENDING) (Lionel will share format)	Lionel Kadja - IITA	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh Prof. Jallo		End of October	1

Set up agreement on ownership of NaSIS with MAFS, SLARI and Njala. (PENDING)	MAFS	Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh	Prof. Allie Kamara	End of October 2025	1
Sharing data of national soil survey including coordinates and metadata. (DONE)	Dr. Chow Khurshid	Prof. Allie Kamara		1 November 2025	1
Add 1-2 page (amendment) on existing MoU between SLARI and Njala University- on data sharing – all new soil data should be added to SIS. (PENDING)		Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh		Mid November to December	1
Assessment of outcome of previous soil survey for SIS development and DSM based on standard metadata format. (PENDING)	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh Prof. Jallo	ISRIC mapping team + Prof. Edward Rhodes		End of November	1
Set up ToR for steering and TOR for technical committee (ISRIC can share template) (PENDING) / DONE	MAFS	Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh	Prof. Allie Kamara	End of November	1
Creating V2 maps based on previous soil data	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh Prof. Jallo	ISRIC mapping team		End of December	1
Review AfricaSIS and its field campaign standards (which uses FAO standards and methods) (ISRIC to share link: https://africasis.isric.org/ and standards: https://africasis.isric.org/procedures.html) (DONE) Page on standards related to Soil Information: https://isric-prod.netlify.app/focus-areas/standards-for-soil-information/		Technical task force: Romaric Prof. Alfa Kamara Prof. Allie Kamara Prof. Edward Rhodes (advisor) Prof Sawyerr		End of December	1

Prof. Allie Kamara send list of names Task Force to WA Hub / DONE		Dr. Alfred Dixon (ex-official) Prof. Jallo ...			
Select standard for soil data collection in SL (based on assessment)		Technical task force		End of December	1
Write up standard in Soil Data Collection Policy for future soil campaigns	MAFS	Technical task force		End of December	1
Set up steering and technical committee (selecting members)	MAFS	Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh	Prof. Allie Kamara	January 2026	1
Set up soil database within Njala university based on AfSIS (ISRIC shares AfSIS database: Africa Soil Profiles Database, version 1.2) / DONE		Dr. Denis Amara		2026	2
Create template data sharing MoU for other stakeholders to add data/info into the SIS		Prof. Rhodes Chief (Dr) Alfred Dixon Prof. Dennis		2026	3
Based on assessment, identify data gaps and sampling design	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh	WA hub + technical task force		2026-2027	
Field campaign and capacity building (also on new standards and method)	Prof. Allie Kamara Dr. Abdul Rahman Conteh	WA hub + technical task force		2026-2027 Best time: Jan & Feb	

Additional recommendations

Based on experiences from other SIS developments, there are additional recommendations that were not discussed during the workshop. These come from a review of the **SIS Framework** (<https://resources.isric.org/sis-framework/>), which includes several elements that may be valuable for Sierra Leone's NaSIS. You can visit the website for further recommendations and detailed guidance.

Consider to:

- Add pollution and contamination as use case for the SIS. This use case is getting more momentum in other countries.
- Research the sustainability of the SIS more detail: who will fund in the short, medium and long term? What are the sensible steps to help answer that and take action to secure funding?
- Use the FAIR process framework to generate the necessary data management and access plan for successful SIS: <https://fairprocessframework.org/>
- Appoint a SIS champion who can drive the SIS development forward and will be the main contact person.
- Engage with potential users, beneficiaries and producers by organising a stakeholder workshop to further understand their needs.
- Develop a communication and engagement plan for the SIS. Who else needs to know about the SIS? How can they be reached? Which stakeholders will support spreading awareness and publicising the SIS?
- Identify risks and plan to mitigate. What are the other potential risks to the system that should be monitored? See: <https://www.smartsheet.com/content/project-risk-assessment>
- Develop an organisational plan. Is there a clear organisational chart for where the SIS fits in? Are the relevant roles to operate and support the long-term operation of the SIS filled?
- Develop a workplan and a budget for the next phase.

Annex 1: Workshop Program

Day 1

Breakfast and registration | 08:00 - 09:30

Session 1: setting the scene | 09:30 -10:00

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Welcome by Moderator	Goals and format for the workshop
	<i>The moderator will introduce each speaker before they speak</i>	
10'	MAFS / SLARI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome remarks The needs for a SIS in Sierra Leone The motivation of the government to develop and own a fully functioning SIS
5'	Njala University	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The need for understanding best practice in the development of soil information systems
5'	IITA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the West Africa Hubs project Goals for the workshop and how it fits with the project activities and goals
2'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key takeaways from initial presentations

Session 2: Introduction to the SIS framework | 10:00 – 10:30

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction, objectives and format of the session
20'	Eng. Thaïsa van der Woude ISRIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to the Framework for Sustainable National Soil Information Systems (SIS Framework) Value of FAIR data principles for SISs
5'	Q&A from the audience Moderator	

Group photo and coffee break | 10:30-11:00

Session 3: Current status of NaSIS and live demo SIS | 11:00 – 12:00

Objective:

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
10'	MAFS / SLARI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Current state of soil information in Sierra Leone Plans and goals for Sierra Leone SIS in the long term

25'	Njala University	<p>Live walkthrough of current NaSIS including land suitability maps (platform or mockup)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the lessons learned? • What are the current functionalities in the SIS? • How is the data security and quality ensured?
20'	Q&A from the audience Moderator	
3'	Moderator	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Session 4: SIS stakeholder map and requirements | 12:00 – 13:00

Objective: To verify the user requirements and use cases beyond fertility maps.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the essential use cases for the SIS? • What is the desired outcome and long-term vision for the SIS? • How can the SIS support Sierra Leone's agricultural policies? • What other stakeholders are exist? What they can contribute to the SIS? How they use the SIS?
3'	Moderator	Key takeaways and preparation for action planning

Networking lunch | 13:00-14:00
Session 5: Data requirements | 14:00 – 15:00

Objective: to identify the data challenges

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How should user permissions and data access be managed? • What are the data challenges? • What are the data requirements from user perspective? • What data policies, strategies and mandates exist? • How can data sharing be achieved between SIS related efforts? • How will trust be built and differences resolved between stakeholders to align approaches to FAIR data standards and policies?
3'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key takeaways

Action planning session 6: Partnership model | 16:00– 18:00

Objective: Identify the key institutional partners needed to implement and sustain the SIS.

Timing	Speakers	Comment / guiding questions
3'	Welcome back by moderator	
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is the owner of the SIS? • Who should be the long-term technical administrator of the SIS? • What institutional arrangement or coordination mechanism is needed to govern the partnership? <i>Should there be a steering committee, technical working group, or lead institution?</i> • How can we ensure that the partnership is inclusive, transparent, and responsive to stakeholder needs over time? • What agreements or commitments (e.g. MoUs, data-sharing protocols) are needed to formalize the collaboration?
<p>The moderator should seek feedback and comments from the audience while the discussion is taking place</p> <p>Moderator</p>		
2'	Moderator	

Close of day 1 | 16:00 – 16:30

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	
5'	MAFS / SLARI	Key takeaways from day 1
5'	Njala University	
5'	IITA	
3'	Moderator	
		Official closure of day 1

Day 2

Welcome and breakfast | 08:00-09:30

Recap of day 1 and opening of day 2 | 09:30-10:00

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
5'	Moderator	Welcome and summary of day 1
5'	Ministry of Agriculture/ SLARI	Opening remarks and reflections of day 1
5'	Moderator	Explanation of day 2 sessions

Session 7: Ideal system design | 10:00 – 11:00

Objective: To understand the requirements and expectations of Sierra Leone NaSIS users to inform the design of technically feasible, user-friendly, and scalable architecture that is FAIR data compliant.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
5'	Moderator	Session Introduction
10'	Dr. Chow Khurshid ISRIC	Soil Information Workflow: possible elements of a SIS
45'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What specific functionalities or features (e.g. dashboards, maps, data security, mobile accessibility, offline access) is missing from the current SIS? • What are you expecting from a soil database? • Where should the database and the SIS be hosted? • Are there any technical capacity gaps?

Coffee break | 11:00 – 11:30

Action planning session 8: Long term sustainability | 11:30 – 14:00

Objectives: Explore financial strategies to ensure the long-term sustainability of Sierra Leone SIS.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Session Introduction
80'	Discussion	<p>Cost Structure – Understanding Financial Needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which institution in Sierra Leone should be responsible for the long-term financial management of the SIS? • What are the key cost categories in the SIS lifecycle (e.g. personnel, tech infrastructure, data management, capacity building)? • What is the estimated cost for the next 1–3 years across the next development phases that the SIS will need to go through (initiation, design, implementation)? • Which costs are already covered (e.g. by the government, funded project Sierra LeoneSIS, etc.) and which are still unfunded?

		<p>Funding Models – Blending Core and Value-Added Financing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What government budget lines could potentially support the SIS (e.g. agriculture, digital infrastructure, environment)? • Could a dedicated SIS funding unit or fundraising mechanism (e.g. grant writing team) be established? <p>Revenue Streams and Public-Private Collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What services or information could the SIS tailor for private sector clients (e.g. fertilizer companies, agribusinesses)? • What types of users (e.g. extension agents, local governments, NGOs) would be willing to pay for enhanced, user-specific data? • Are there existing consulting, training, or soil analysis services that SIS could build upon to generate income?
3'	Moderator	Key takeaways

Networking lunch | 14:00 – 15:00

Session 10: Finalizing next steps and action items | 15:00 – 16:00

Objective: To consolidate insights from the sessions and outline a clear, actionable path forward for the Sierra Leone SIS development roadmap, focusing on prioritizing activities, assigning responsibilities, and establishing timelines.

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
2'	Moderator	Session Introduction
55'	Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the immediate action items based on the discussions in the previous sessions? • Which short-term priorities should be addressed first, and what is the timeline for each? • Who will be responsible for each key action, and how can accountability be ensured?
3'	Moderator	Key takeaways

Close of day 2 | 16:00 – 16:15

Timing	Speaker	Comment / guiding questions
5'	Moderator	
5'	IITA	Takeaways from the two-day workshop
5'	Njala University	
5'	Ministry of Agriculture / SLARI	Official closure of the workshop; closing remarks

Annex 2: Flipcharts from different groups

Group B ①

1) What specific functionalities do you want to see in your SIS or what is missing from the current SIS?

What is missing?

- No Data Base Central data base.
- Insufficient Data (Missing Parameters)
- No Current Established SIS.

What Do we want to see in the SIS?

- To secure an office
- Access to Soil data (Raw data), Climate data and Land use.
- Interactive ^{soil profiles + soil info} ~~maps~~ Maps on Soil health Properties/General Crop Recommendations.
- Agronomic data (yield data) ^{Rice advice recommendations} _{↳ from other countries to display to SL}
- Fertilizer Recommendation
- Access to decision support systems
- Login Feature (levels of accessibility)

Group B ②

2) What are you expecting the SIS will serve?

- Crop Recommendation.
- Soil Health Information.
- Fertilizer Recommendation.
- Downloadable Maps.
- Policy briefs (Data Summary board, graphics, tables etc) DASH

3) Where should the Data base and the SIS be hosted?

- Njala University - Department of Soil Science (because it is closer to the experts)

4) Are there any technical capacity Gaps?

- Trained ICT personnel to maintain and operate the system.
- Data Curator
- Administrative staff.
- GIS Expert in digital soil mapping and Remote Sensing Expert.

Group A ①

Long term sustainability

Institution for long-term financial mgt. of SIS in SL

- MAFS
- SLARI
- NU

Key cost categories in the SIS life cycle

- personnel cost (salaries)
- Technical Infrastructure e.g. Cloud services
- Training & Capacity building (Short & long-term training)
- Operational cost

Group A ②

Costs already covered

- personnel cost

Government budget lines that could potentially support SIS

- Potential institutional overhead (\$50,000-70,000)

Dedicated funding raising mechanism to the establish SIS

- Cost percentage allocation to SIS

1. Yes
2. SLARI & NU.
3. Yearly Subscription

Group A ③

Services/Information the SIS could provide for Private Sector

- Soil fertility mapping
- Land use planning & mgt
- Fertilizer Recommendation
- Input data for AI

Type of users willing to pay

- Fertilizer Companies
- Investment Consultancy
- A.I e.g. google services

Existing consulting, training or soil analysis could be led upon to generate income

- YES
- Quality Control lab for NU & SLARI
-
-

GROUP A

Specific functionality we want to see in the SIS

- Interactive web map
- ~~Area~~
- Soil health monitoring Dashboard
- Functionality for updating and uploading additional data by technical lead
- Data Security - backup
- Offline accessibility

Expectations for the SIS

1. Safe repository of data for the national soil data
2. Streamline for investment/target intervention.
3. Guide for Policy formulation

Feedback
SIS system: How does a functional SIS system work for s/l to make inputs in terms of addition or subtraction of information

GROUP A

SIS hosting

Technical

SLARI Co-hosting with NH.

Software

- Cloud based
- easy access & security

Technical Capacity Gaps

- GIS specialist/Geospatial analyst
- Data management expert
- I.T. expert
- Software developer
- Programmer
- Soil Scientist
- Data Scientist
- Lab analyst

Feed

Group B ①

1) Which Institution in s/l should be responsible for the long-term financial Management of the SIS?

- National budget # the NHHS
- University employ SIS staff payed by the government
- All Stakeholders Institution Combs Part of their budget to Support SIS
- Monetized some of the services of the SIS or Deep Analysis
- To establish SIS as a National Agency

2) What are the key cost categories in the SIS life cycle (eg personnel, tech infrastructure, data management, capacity building)

Group B ②

- Per Sonne
- Infrastructure (Electronic (Computers, softwares, Server building)
- Operation Cost like maintenance, update

3) Which Cost are already Covered, and are still Pending

- Office space, electricity and other utilities
- Raw Data

Pending

- Capacity building

4) What government budget lines could potentially support the SIS (eg agriculture, digital infrastructure, environment?)

- Create a new budget line for the SIS from the relevant stakeholders.

Group B ③

5) Could a dedicated SIS funding unit or Fund raising mechanism (eg grant writing team) be established

- Employ a Project and Grant officer
- Soil analysis lab fee factor a small fee on lab analysis to fund SIS

6) What Services or Information could the SIS allow for private sector clients (eg Fertilizer Companies, Agribusinesses)?

- Agricultural Companies - Fertilizer recommendation, Soil/crops suitability Maps, soil data, legacy data
- Fertilizer Companies - Soil data for site specific/crop specific fertilizer formulation
- Agribusiness Investment crop site suitability

7) Are there existing Consulting, training or

Group B ④

7) What type of users (eg extension agents, local governments, NGOs) would be willing to pay for enhanced, user specific data?

- Limited Advertisers especially from private sector.
- Research Scientist/Projects.

8) Are there existing Consulting, training, or social analysis services that SIS could build upon to generate more?

- Staff of BISHIA Consultants
- Existing consultants

GROUP C

Q1: MAFS & RESEARCH INSTITUTES

Q2: PERSONNEL (GIS DATA MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT)

INFRASTRUCTURE (SOFTWARE COMP HARDWARE, DATA STORAGE, SOIL LAB)

Q3: LAB - FEW FEW - EQUIPMENT - SOME TECHNICAL PERSONNEL

GROUP C

Q3 UNFUNDED

OPERATIONAL COST

PERSONNEL COST

RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT COST

CAPACITY BUILDING

MORE EQUIPMENT

GROUP C

Q4: MAFS (AGRICULTURE) MINISTERS

Q5: "YES"

"BECAUSE GOVERNMENT FUNDING ARE NOT ENOUGH"

MORE MONEY !!!
 MORE WORK !!!

Q6:

- * TRAINING WORKSHOP CONSULTATION
- * SOIL & CROP DATA, STATISTICS
- * LAND USE PLANNING
- * CLIMATE CHANGE INFO.
- * R&D SUPPORT

Q7: AGR. PRODUCERS

- * LAND MANAGEMENT - AGR. BUSINESS
- * INTERNATIONAL - AGR. BUSINESSES * NGOs
- * AGR. INPUT COMPANIES
- * FINANCIAL INSTITUTION (NBFCs)

Q8: CONSULTANCY

- LAB SERVICES
- SHORT TERM COURSES
- DATA INSIGHTS
- IP of SOFTWARE

Annex 3: List of Participants

Number	Name	Organization	Designation	Role in SILSIS
1	Dr Abdul Conteh	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Director-General	SIS Owners
2	Dr Alfred Dixon	IITA-Sierra Leone	IITA-Representative	SIS Owners
3	Dr Alie Kamara	Njala University	Professor of Soil Science	SIS Owners
4	Dr. Denis M.K Amara	Njala university	Professor of Soil Science	SIS Owners
5	Professor Abdulai Jalloh	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS)	Chief Agricultural Officer	Enabling Environment
6	Dr Prince Norman	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Deputy Director-General	SIS Owners
7	Dr Isata Kamanda	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Deputy Director-General	SIS Owners
8	Professor Patrick Sawyerr	Njala University	Professor of Pedology	SIS Owners
9	Mr Foday Suma	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Soil Scientist	SIS Owners
10	Professor Edward R. Rhodes	Emeritus Professor, Njala University	Emeritus Professor in soils	SIS Owners
11	Mr Raymond Massaquoi	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Soil and Water Engineer	SIS Owners
12	Mohamed Lamin Sesay	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Environmental Scientist	SIS Owners
13	Abdul Sesay	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Soil and Water Engineer	SIS Owners
14	Dr Andrew BaMusa Koroma	National Fertilizer Regulatory Agency (NaFRA)	Executive Director	Enabling Environment
15	Dr. Mohamed Blango	Njala University	Professor of Irrigation	SIS Owners
16	Mr Hindolo Bebeley	Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI)	Soil and Water Engineer	SIS Owners
17	Mr Ishmael Tarawalli	Division of Agricultural Engineering and Mechanization	Soil and Water Engineer	Enabling Environment
18	Mr John Kamara	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS)	Head of Crops Division	Enabling Environment
19	Mr Yahya Mansaray	Ministry of Agriculture and Food Security (MAFS)	Head of Extension Division	Users
20	Dr Kepifri Lakoh	Food Systems Resilience Programme (FSRP)	Project Manager	Users
21	Dr Robert Chakanda	Sierra Leone Seed Certification Agency (SLeSCA)	Executive Director	Enabling Environment
22	Dr. A. Y. Kamara	IITA-Kano	Systems Agronomists	Enabling Environment
23	Dr. Aloysius Beah	National Fertilizer Regulatory Agency (NaFRA)	Compliance Manager	Enabling Environment

24	Madam Monica Kwame-Greene	Agricultural Value Chain Development Project (AVDP)	Project Manager	Users
25	Madam Yatta Sama	National Federation of Farmers of Sierra Leone (NaFFSL)	President of Farmers' Federation	Users
26	Mr Abdulai Wai	Regional Rice Value Chain Project (S.L.)	Project Manager	Users
27	Mr John Sinah	Rice Agro-Industrial Cluster Project (RAIC-SL)	Project Manager	Users
28	Mr Tamba Jumu	SLARIS Project	Project Manager	Users